

New information on the crowned crab spider *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* Jézéquel, 1966 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT

The crowned crab spider *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* Jézéquel, 1966 has been recorded from South Africa, extending its current distribution range in Africa from the Ivory Coast to South Africa. Very little is known about the species and although widely distributed in South Africa, they are not very commonly found. The general morphology of the species is described and photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parasmodix* is monotypic and presently only known from *P. quadrituberculata* from the Ivory Coast (World Spider Catalog, 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys are undertaken to document the South African spider fauna. Some of the material sampled were identified as *P. quadrituberculata*.

Except for the original description nothing is known about the species. In this paper we provide some information on their morphology based on photographs of live specimens, behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

SANSAs surveys were undertaken throughout the country and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

TAXONOMY

Parasmodix quadrituberculata Jézéquel, 1966

Parasmodix quadrituberculatus Jézéquel, 1966: 628, f. 19-22

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female 4-5 mm. Carapace as wide as long (Fig. 1); chestnut brown with white band around carapace border (Fig. 2); with scattered short setae and a few longer setae present on truncated posterior edge of carapace, on clypeal edge and between lateral eyes and behind posterior lateral eyes; cephalic region high and slightly convex, sloping anteriorly; thoracic region truncated posteriorly (Fig. 2); eyes in two rows covering most of carapace width; both eye rows recurved (Fig. 7); anterior eye row slightly narrower than posterior eye row (Fig. 3); lateral eyes large with anterior median eyes smallest (Fig. 3); chelicerae with dorsal surface slightly flattened (Fig. 6); cheliceral ridge with upper edge rounded and slightly protruding with 7-9 inwardly curved spiniform setae. Abdomen oval; mottled with white and dark markings; lateral sides with white bands. Legs are pale yellow; femora and patellae of legs I and II dark brown; other legs with brown spots and lines (Fig. 8).

Figures 1-3. *Parasmodix quadrituberculata* female from Enseleni Nature Reserve 1. Female dorsal view 2. Female lateral view 3. Female anterior view. Photo credits: Ruan Booysen.

Figures 4-8. *Parasmoxid quadrituberculata*. 4. Female epigyne ventral view. 5. Female habitus. 6. Female carapace and eye pattern dorsal view. 8. Female habitus. Photo credits: 4. Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman 5-6. Robin Lyle 7-8. Ronel White.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Ivory Coast and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Gauteng: Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest (-28.31, 32.37); Isandlwana Nature Reserve (-28.36, 30.64); Mkhomazi State Forest (-29.62, 29.75); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.70); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Tuinplaas (-24.90, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **North West:** Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75). **Western Cape:** Du Toits Kloof (-33.70, 19.27); 40 km NE Ceres, Touwsriver road (-33.36, 19.31).

Figure 9. South African records of *Parasmoxid quadrituberculata*.

BEHAVIOUR

They are free-living plant-dwelling spiders that are more commonly found on shrubs, herbs and trees. They are well camouflaged and blend in with the vegetation. Very little is known about their behaviour and although widely distributed, they are not very commonly found.

They are usually sampled with sweeping and beating of the vegetation from the Grassland, Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savannah biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011; 2013). Also sampled from maize fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). Adults were sampled throughout the year, and juveniles were sampled from May until October.

CONSERVATION STATUS

There are no significant threats to the species. Recorded from eight reserves such as Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2009), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2009), Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

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